

PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE PANELS SUBJECTED TO UNDERWATER IMPULSIVE LOADING

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SUMMARY

Optimization of the overall blast resistance of naval hulls made of composite materials relies on the ability of the structure to resist underwater explosion by energy dissipation. In this work, the performance of a composite solid panel is studied by numerical simulations, to estimate admissible loads and to capture dissipation mechanisms associated with the damage of the composite material.

Keywords: Fluid Structure Interaction, Composite panels, Impulsive Loading

1. INTRODUCTION

The blast resistance of naval hulls is a critical engineering problem being widely investigated for the design of next generation of marine vessels. Moreover, blast protection plays an increasingly crucial role in engineering civil transportation. Two different architectures are generally used to build composite hulls: the framed single-skin design, and the sandwich construction, where a crushable core is encased between fiber-reinforced face skins. These types of hulls have been characterized by numerical simulations, where an underwater blast impacts the structure [1-3]. On the experimental side, fluid-structure interaction (FSI) experiments have been successfully scaled-down to be realized inside a research laboratory [4, 5]. In this work, we model a composite panel subjected to impulsive loads to gain insight into the design of fluid-structure interaction experiments to be carried out in the future.

2. COMPOSITE PANEL MODELING

In this preliminary study, we assess the response of a monolithic composite panel subjected to underwater blast loadings (Fig. 1a), where fluid structure interaction (FSI) is present. The impulse is characterized by the characteristic decay time t_0 and by its peak pressure p_0 (Fig. 1b). The panel is composed of E-glass plies stacked following a quasi isotropic layup scheme, and infused with a vinylester resin. These matrix and fibre materials were chosen for their low cost and also because of their waterproof abilities; indeed they represent materials of interest for the construction of naval hulls. The geometry of the panel is defined by a radius of 76.2 mm, which corresponds to the configuration used in the experimental fluid structure interaction setup [4, 5]. The simulations are performed using Abaqus/Explicit. Water is modelled with linear

Hugoniot equation of state and contact between the specimen and water was modeled with a balanced master/slave algorithm enforced kinematically.

Figure 1: Model description of the multiply composite panel submitted to underwater blast load.

2.1. Panel description

In the scaled-down experimental apparatus described in [4, 5], steel monolithic and sandwich panels with an areal mass ranging from 11 to 14 kg/m² were tested. To allow a comparison in the same range of impulse per mass per unit area, an areal mass of 11 kg/m² is chosen here for the composite panel. For a typical areal mass per ply of 300g/m², a 36 ply layup gives a suitable weight. The layup stacking sequence is (0/45/90/-45)₄-(45/90/-45/0)₅, with a thickness per ply of 0.168mm. The panel plies are modeled with the Hashin damage initiation criterion [6]. The initiation criteria are independent in the fibers and the matrix, and depend on the stress state. Once an initiation criterion is met, a linear softening damage evolution begins [7]. The adhesive layers between the plies are modeled with zero-thickness traction-separation cohesive elements [8-11]. The panel plies are meshed with SC8R continuum shell elements, the adhesive layers are meshed with COH3D8 cohesive elements, and the water has an adaptive mesh of C3D8R elements. The numerical model possesses ~10⁶ degrees of freedom.

2.2. Composite plies

Each composite ply is modelled as unidirectional lamina with properties of E-glass vinylester obtained from [12, 13] (see Table 1).

Table 1: properties of E-glass vinylester unidirectional lamina

E ₁₁ (GPa)	E ₂₂ (GPa)	ν ₁₂	G ₁₂ (GPa)	G ₁₃ (GPa)	G ₂₃ (GPa)	X ^T (MPa)	X ^C (MPa)
39	12	0.28	3.5	3	3	1100	620
Y ^T (MPa)	Y ^C (MPa)	S ^L (MPa)	S ^T (MPa)	α	G _r (N/mm)	G _m (N/mm)	ρ (kg/m ³)
39	128	89	60	1	12.5	1	2100

In the above table, E_{11} and E_{22} stand for the longitudinal and transverse Young's modulus, respectively; ν_{12} is the Poisson's ratio, G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus, G_{13} and G_{23} are the out of plane shear moduli, X^T and X^C are the fiber tensile and compressive strengths, Y^T and Y^C are the matrix tensile and compressive strengths, S^L is the in-plane shear strength, and S^T is the out of plane shear strength. The parameter α determines the contribution of the shear stress to the fiber tensile damage initiation criterion and is described in [6, 7]. The parameters G_f and G_m stand for the energy release rates associated to the fiber and the matrix, respectively.

2.3. Adhesive layers

The plies of the composite panel are bonded together with the resin used for infusion. Properties of the adhesive layers were obtained for a vinylester resin, based on interlaminar fracture characterization conducted in [12]. The Young's modulus of the resin in the model is 3.5GPa and its Poisson ratio is 0.33. The behavior of the adhesive layers was modeled by zero thickness traction separation cohesive elements [8-11], and the penalty stiffness are scaled by a nominal thickness $T_0 = 5 \mu\text{m}$. Damage in the cohesive element initiates when a quadratic strain criterion is met, calibrated to correspond to the tensile strength of $\sigma_0=70\text{MPa}$ observed on that material. The interlaminar fracture toughness $G_0 = 1.23 \text{ N/mm}$ was derived from the stress concentration factor of $0.694\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ reported in [12].

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

In the simulation results presented hereafter, the time origin corresponds to the time the impulse reaches the panel, after propagating in the water column, which has a length $h_w=494 \text{ mm}$. Such length allows 666 ms to elapse after the primary blast wave reaches the specimen and before a secondary wave is reflected towards the specimen.

3.1. Deflection profiles evolution and damage maps

Different impulses have been applied to the composite panels. The decay time t_0 is kept constant at $25\mu\text{s}$ to satisfy the scaling constraints developed in [4], and the peak pressures p_0 was varied from 30MPa to 70MPa. Figure 2a and b presents the evolution of normalized deflection δ/L (out of plane displacement divided by the radius) plotted across a diameter of the panel back face for 50 MPa and 70 MPa, respectively. For easy comparison, the scales are identical in the two plots and the profiles are plotted for the same time instances. The responses show similar trends but different amplitudes. The deflection progresses from the clamped area of the panel towards its center. For $p_0=50 \text{ MPa}$ (75MPa), at $27\mu\text{s}$ and $147\mu\text{s}$, the peak deflection is attained on the periphery of the panel at $r=58.5\text{mm}$ (56mm) and $r=43.2\text{mm}$ (45.8mm), respectively. At later times, the peak deflection is observed in the center of the panel. For $p_0=70 \text{ MPa}$, the deflection profile is sharper than the one obtained for $p_0=50\text{MPa}$, and the elastic spring back of the panel at $t=667\mu\text{s}$ is more significant at higher impulse.

Figure 2: Deflection profiles obtained for 50 and 70MPa peak pressure impulses

For an impulse of peak pressure $p_0=50\text{MPa}$, Hashin damage initiation criterion maps, for the last ply of the layup (on the airside of the panel), are reported in Figure 3a and Figure 3b for the fiber tension and the matrix tension, respectively. Coordinate system reference vectors x_1 (0° ply angle) and x_2 (90° ply angle) are included in the plots. While the initiation criterion does not exceed 0.18 for the fiber tension, it reaches 1 in most of the panel for matrix tension. The back face of the panel undergoes biaxial stretching; hence, extensive matrix damage is expected to occur before fiber damage. Note that the applied impulse is not sufficient to induced fiber damage in the airside ply. Damage values in the matrix reaching 1 (i.e., complete damage) are observed in the back face, but since fibers are still undamaged, failure is prevented.

Figure 3: Hashin damage initiation criterions for (a): fiber tension (HSNFTCRT), and (b): matrix tension (HSNMTCRT), for $p_0=50\text{MPa}$

3.2. Sensitivity to impulse peak pressure

The time evolutions of non-dimensional deflection δ_c/L are reported in Figure 4 for peak pressures p_0 varying from 30 to 70 MPa. These evolutions show an increase in both maximum deflection δ_{\max} and elastic spring back with increasing peak pressure p_0 .

As expected, the higher the far field impulse $I_0=p_0t_0$, the higher is the impulse imparted on the composite panel. This is reflected in a faster attainment in maximum center deflection, which is shown with a circle in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Center deflection evolution of the panel at different impulses. The maximum center deflection is indicated with a circle.

Dissipated energies by damage in the composite plies and the adhesive layers, are plotted in Figure 5a and Figure 5b, respectively. The intralaminar dissipated energy E_d^{intra} is 25 times higher than the interlaminar dissipated energy E_d^{inter} , hence the total dissipated energy mostly depends on the damage in the plies, and does not significantly depend on the energies involved in the delamination process. Figure 5a shows that energy is dissipated progressively in the lamina whereas most of the energy is dissipated in the first 200 μ s in the adhesive layers (Figure 5b).

(a) intralaminar dissipated energy

(b) interlaminar dissipated energy

Figure 5: Energies dissipated in the composite panel for different impulses. The common legend is indicated in plot (b).

In Figure 5b, we can notice a positive ramp of low dissipation rate at negative times (before the impulse reaches the panel). This spurious effect is likely due to numerical noise in the contact algorithm and the high stiffness in the cohesive elements. However, this contribution remains negligible when compared to the sharp increase in interlaminar dissipated energy occurring after the blast wave reaches the panel.

Figure 6: Total dissipated energy as function of peak pressure

The total dissipated energy $E_d^{\text{total}} = E_d^{\text{inter}} + E_d^{\text{intra}}$ is reported in Figure 6 as a function of peak pressure p_0 . Dissipated energy shows a quadratic evolution $\tilde{E}_d(p_0)$ of the total dissipated energy levels with the peak pressure, for which the polynomial fit is represented with a dashed line. The identified polynomial coefficients are $a = 1.674 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1/2}$, $b = -0.857 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1}$, $c = 12.41 \text{ kJ}$. At 70 MPa peak pressure, a dissipated energy of 34.3 kJ is obtained.

3.3. Influence of interlaminar fracture toughness and strength

In view that interlaminar properties are scarce in the literature and tend to exhibit variations due to adhesive chemistry and manufacturing processes, we perform in this section a parametric study investigating the effect of strength and toughness variability of the adhesive layers in the panel performance. The nominal values of strength σ_0 and toughness G_0 are 70 MPa and 1.23 N/mm, respectively, and variations of $\pm 30\%$ are considered for each of the parameters, independently. For these five sets of parameters, the same impulse ($t_0 = 25 \mu\text{s}$, $p_0 = 50 \text{ MPa}$) was applied. The resulting intralaminar and interlaminar dissipated energies are plotted in Figure 7a and Figure 7b.

As expected, higher interlaminar fracture toughness leads to a decrease in the energy dissipated in the adhesive, Figure 7b, and lower toughness produces the opposite effect. When the interface strength is changed, the interlaminar dissipated energy increases for both weaker and stronger interfaces, Figure 7b. A smaller increase is observed for the case of a stronger interface.

Two main trends can be observed regarding the intralaminar dissipated energy reported in Figure 7a. Dissipation in the laminae is reduced by 9.5% when increasing the toughness of the adhesive layers by 30%, and it is increased by 3.2% when reducing the strength in the adhesive layers.

Figure 7: Energies dissipated in the composite panel for different adhesive strength σ_0 and different fracture toughness G_0 . The common legend is indicated in plot (a).

3.4. Influence of intralaminar fracture toughness

Following a similar approach as the one developed in section 3.3, a parametric study is here performed to investigate the effect of toughness variability of the composite plies in panel performance. The nominal values of fracture toughness in the fibres and matrix are 12.5N/mm and 1N/mm, respectively. Simultaneous variations of $\pm 30\%$ are considered for both of the parameters.

The different dissipated energy evolutions obtained with the toughness variations in the plies are presented in Figure 8. While the interlaminar dissipated energy remains almost unchanged by the latter variations, changes are observed in intralaminar dissipated energy, Figure 8a. Reducing the ply toughness by 30% increases the dissipated energy by 12.36%, and increasing the ply toughness by 30% decreases the dissipated energy by 7.43%.

Figure 8: Energies dissipated in the composite panel for different fiber fracture toughness G_f and matrix fracture toughness G_m .

3.5. Evolution of the peak deflection for different fracture toughness and strength

Variations of dissipated energies were observed and discussed in sections 3.3 and 3.4. To complete this study, the peak deflection evolutions are plotted in Figure 9 for the different fracture toughnesses and strengths introduced in the aforementioned sections. While dissipated energies were influenced by the model parameter variations, peak deflection evolutions are almost constant for these different dissipative systems. This feature is important in the performance evaluation of the composite panel.

Figure 9: Peak deflection evolutions for different fracture strength and toughness in the composite plies and in the adhesive layers.

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

- Simulation results presented in this paper can be used to guide the selection of experimental parameters to be used in fluid-structure interaction experiments. The response of monolithic panels has been identified for several peak pressures and interface properties.
- From the presented numerical results, deflection profiles evolutions show that the monolithic composite panel investigated exhibit 3 times less deflection than A304 stainless steel monolithic panels for a similar impulse [4]. The elastic spring back of the damaged panel is also significant as compared to steels because dissipated energy is associated to a stiffness reduction instead of a plastic flow. If confirmed experimentally, this feature would demonstrate the abilities of composite materials to sustain blast loadings with limited deflection and shape recovery abilities.
- Dissipated energy has a quadratic evolution with the impulse peak pressure.
- Preliminary trends in dissipated energy variations as a function of ply and adhesive characteristics were determined by conducting a parametric study. For a given impulse, higher interlaminar and intralaminar fracture toughnesses

results in a decrease in dissipated energy, whereas a lower intralaminar fracture toughness or interlaminar fracture strength produces the opposite effect. The results presented in this paper are encouraging and further analysis will be conducted to better understand the relationships between constituent properties and the performance of composite panels subjected to underwater impulsive loading.

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References

- [1] Deshpande VS, Fleck NA. One-dimensional response of sandwich plates to underwater shock loading. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 2005;53(11):2347-2383.
- [2] Hoo Fatt MS, Palla L. Analytical Modeling of Composite Sandwich Panels under Blast Loads. submitted to *J of Sandwich Struct and Mat*.
- [3] Tilbrook MT, Deshpande VS, Fleck NA. Underwater blast loading of sandwich beams: regimes of behaviour. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*; In Press, Accepted Manuscript.
- [4] Espinosa H, Lee S, Moldovan N. A Novel Fluid Structure Interaction Experiment to Investigate Deformation of Structural Elements Subjected to Impulsive Loading. *Experimental Mechanics* 2006;46(6):805-824.
- [5] Mori LF, Lee S, Xue ZY, Vaziri A, Queheillalt DT, Dharmasena KP, Wadley HNG, Hutchinson JW, Espinosa HD. Deformation and fracture modes of sandwich structures subjected to underwater impulsive loads. *J Mech Mater Struct* 2007;2(10):1981-2006.
- [6] Hashin Z. Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites. *J Appl Mech-Trans ASME* 1980;47(2):329-334.
- [7] Abaqus Analysis User's Manual. Corp. DSS, editor. Providence, RI, USA, 2008.
- [8] Dwivedi SK, Espinosa HD. Modeling dynamic crack propagation in fiber reinforced composites including frictional effects. *Symposium on Experiments and Modeling of Failure of Modern Materials San Diego, California: Elsevier Science Bv*, 2001, pp. 481-509.
- [9] Dwivedi SK, Espinosa HD. Modeling Intersonic Crack Propagation in Fiber Reinforced Composites with Contact/Cohesive Laws. *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*. Waas AM, Whitcomb JD, editors. New York, 2001, pp. 121-153.
- [10] Espinosa HD, Lu HC, Zavattieri PD, Dwivedi S. A 3-D Finite Deformation Anisotropic Visco-Plasticity Model for Fiber Composites. *J Compos Mater* 2001;35(5):369-410.

- [11] Camanho PP, Davila CG, de Moura MF. Numerical simulation of mixed-mode progressive delamination in composite materials. *J Compos Mater* 2003;37(16):1415-1438.
- [12] Compston P, Jar PYB, Davies P. Matrix effect on the static and dynamic interlaminar fracture toughness of glass-fibre marine composites. *Compos Pt B-Eng* 1998;29(4):505-516.
- [13] Daniel IM, Ishai O. *Engineering Mechanics of Composite Materials*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2005.